

Belgium | One Health Surveillance | Zoonotic influenza

Background

- Clinical surveillance of influenza in humans and avian species has been operating for decades. In contrast, there is no pro-active systematic surveillance of potential transmission of animal (swine or avian) influenza viruses to humans

Objective

- Setting-up pro-active surveillance systems as a pilot-project studies (ZOOIS) to detect asymptomatic cases in at risk workers and implement virological and serological follow-up

Outcomes & Impact

- High acceptance and participation rate in the pilot studies with the exemption of poultry farmers, who were replaced by poultry veterinarians
- New harmonized case definition for management of zoonotic influenza outbreaks, public health recommendations for human cases.
- Improved data and communication flows between federated health authorities, the NRC, the NRL and the Epidemiology of infectious diseases department of Sciensano

Lessons learned

- Recommend including sampling when symptoms appeared and involve various types of veterinarians and include everybody exposed to animal influenza: take all of this into account for ethical approval
- Development of an outbreak and investigation protocol requires multidisciplinary expertise
- Invest in network development (maintaining and nurturing) and coordination to align the different areas of expertise

Core messages

- Including the right sentinel sectors for monitoring is crucial for effective surveillance of animal influenza transmission risks
- Developing and regularly updating a zoonotic influenza outbreak protocol is essential to strengthen preparedness, response operations, and surveillance
- Limited scientific literature and evidence makes challenging to develop guidance particularly within the complex framework of multi-level governance